

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

A homeobox factor that supports metastasis to the brain.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We describe here identification of a homeobox transcription factor, SOX11, that functions to support metastasis to the central nervous system (CNS) in humans with breast cancer. SOX11 was a defining transcription factor of the HER2+ lineage (subtype) in breast cancer; its expression appears obligatory for commitment to the HER2+ subtype. In multiple breast cancer cohorts, SOX11 was activated in CNS metastasis. A second homeobox factor, HOXC10, fulfilled these criteria but evidence suggested it functioned primarily to support transformation and maintenance of transformation rather in a CNS-specific role. Study of brain cancers revealed SOX11 was a human glioblastoma gene. This, we demonstrate here that a factor whose expression is enriched in the primary tumors of humans with HER2+ breast cancer is a CNS metastasis homeobox factor, indicating the presence of factors outside of the recently described HER2+ CNS locus that support metastasis to the brain in humans with breast cancer.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Results

Figure 1: SOX11 is activated in metastasis to the CNS in humans with metastatic breast cancer

GSE191230
GSE100534
GSE52604

Figure 2: SOX11 is a HER2+ lineage homeobox factor in breast cancer.

The data demonstrated that a factor whose expression is enriched in the primary tumors of humans with HER2+ breast cancer was a CNS metastasis homeobox factor, indicating the presence of factors outside of the recently described HER2+ CNS locus that support metastasis to the brain in humans with breast cancer.

GSE45827
GSE87049

Figure 3: GSE116520: SOX11 is activated in human glioblastoma.

.....indicating a role for SOX11 in supporting de novo transformation in the brain rather than a simple metastasis-enhancing factor.

Figure 4: HOXC10, a second homeobox factor whose expression is enriched in the primary tumors of humans with HER2+ breast cancer and activating in CNS metastasis.

We recently demonstrated a role for homeobox transcription factors of the HOXC locus in supporting transformation in general, suggesting HOXC10 activation might play a secondary role in maintaining a transformed state in CNS metastasis rather than specifying or promoting CNS metastasis proper.

Datasets utilized for discussion:

GSE166823: Sox11 siRNA in human iPS
GSE52892: Sox11+ fraction; mantle cell lymphoma xenograft.
Mamoor, 2025. TCF/Lef factors specify subtype in breast cancer.

Discussion

SOX11 regulates expression of genes important for lineage commitment following transformation of the breast, otherwise known as subtype selection, in human breast cancer by regulating expression of nuclear factors that control this process, including TCF3 and TCF7L2.

(The preceding statement (above) concerns relationship between SOX11 expression and a description of TCF7L1/L2 and TCF3 control of subtype selection).

The 2nd element of that statement is most relevant to the evidence provided here:: “SOX11 supports metastasis to the CNS by facilitating subtype selection...of a subtype that is intrinsically biased towards CNS metastasis.”